

Opening the university for seniors: A possibility for inclusive mathematics education

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This paper presents research results on mathematics education with seniors. The research took place in a program entitled Universidade Aberta à Terceira Idade (UnATI, Open University to Seniors). The aim of UnATI is to open the university to the neighborhood community offering activities organized based on the knowledge produced by the university. Our research group has been investigating the contribution of mathematics education in such program. Our main concern is social inclusion in a general perspective. The results allow us to identify the contribution in aspects such as: social representation of mathematics, quality of life, intergenerational relationship. Each one of these aspects are detailed in the text.

Introduction

Research with seniors took place in a program entitled Universidade Aberta à Terceira Idade (UnATI) (Open University to Seniors). The aim of UnATI is to open the university to the neighbourhood community offering activities specially organized for it based on the knowledge produced by the university. In Brazil, according to the Elderly Statute¹, elderly people are those aged over 60 years.

Since 2011, the Épura research group² has been investigating the contribution of Mathematics Education in such program. We have been running two different activities with seniors: *Encontro com a Matemática* (Meeting with Mathematics) and *Encontro com a informática* (Meeting with informatics). The meetings took place every second week during the school year. They took place in the department of Mathematics Education at Universidade Estadual Paulista (Unesp). The research data were produced during these meetings. We have used video, notes and interviews. In this paper we concentrate on data produced in the *Encontro com a Matemática*.

¹ Law No. 10,741, of October 1, 2003, is intended to regulate the guaranteed rights of people aged over 60 years.

² <https://igce.rc.unesp.br/#!/departamentos/educacao-matematica/grupos-de-pesquisa/epura/apresentacao>

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Universidade Aberta à Terceira Idade (UnATI)

The Universidade Aberta à Terceira Idade (UnATI) is an extension program coordinated by the Pró-reitoria de Extensão Universitária e Cultura (PROEX). It is running simultaneously in 20 campuses of Unesp³. Each campus has the autonomy to develop the activities according to the demand of its community and to the research area developed in the campus.

UnATI at Rio Claro has been mainly associated to the Physical Education Department. In 2011 Mathematics Education started a partnership with physical education promoting meetings in which were proposed activities as games, challenges and exploratory tasks. The team responsible for carrying out these activities were constituted by researchers from the university, Master and PhD students from the graduate program in Mathematics Education and undergraduate students in Mathematics. During the first years the meetings were entitled *Conversas sobre Matemática* (*Conversations about Mathematics*) changing to *Encontro com a Matemática* (*Meeting with Mathematics*) in the last years⁴.

This article presents results of the analysis of three activities of the *Encontro com a Matemática*. This analysis highlights the contributions of the development of Mathematics activities with elderly people.

Encontro com a matemática

This activity took place in the laboratory of Mathematics Education of the Department of Mathematics Education at Unesp. It was announced in social media and e-mail lists. There was no need for prior registration in order to participate. It was sufficient to come to the laboratory at the agreed time with disposition to talk about Mathematics. At every meeting, a new subject was approached together with the participants, like; exploring the Tangram; exploring a calculator; math magic; forms in mirrors; reading and discussing numeric and graphic information; Mathematics Bingo.

The participant's school level was remarkably diverse. Some had never attended school and others had college degrees. Some had a problematic relationship with Mathematics as a result of failing school due to Mathematics, and others had sympathized with Mathematics, but never had the opportunity to study. Those who think of Mathematics with a positive perspective saw the *Encontro* as a chance to make a dream come true. Luis (64), one of the participants, revealed to us a bit about the condition of the senior. He tells:

[A minha trajetória escolar] foi sofrida porque morava no sítio. Naquele tempo, não tinha como, a gente precisava andar sete quilômetros [para chegar à escola]. E sete quilômetros para voltar [da escola para casa]. Ia e voltava a pé. Chuva, sol. Eu gostava de lá. [Na escola] eu gostava da professora, dos amigos. Aprender [a] ler, aprender [a] escrever, aprender [a] fazer contas [de Matemática]. Isso tudo era bom, mas era sofrido chegar [à escola]. Estudei até o terceiro ano. Depois, a outra [escola] era mais longe, daí não dava para ir. [Ent]. (Lima, 2015, pp. 104–105)

³ Unesp has 24 campi.

⁴ More details are in Lima (2015) and Scagion (2018).

Opening the university for seniors: A possibility for inclusive mathematics education

[My scholar trajectory] was suffering because I lived in a farm in the countryside. At that time, there was no possibility, we needed to walk seven kilometers [to reach the school]. I would come and go walking. Rain, sun. I liked there. [At school] I liked the teacher, the friends. Learning [to] read, learning [to] write, learning [to] make calculations [of Mathematics]. All that was good but suffered to reach [the school]. I studied until the third grade. After that, the other [school] was too far away, then I could not go. (Lima, 2015, pp. 104–105, our translation)

The meetings were mediated by a dialogical and investigative approach according to Alrø and Skovsmose (2004) and Freire (2011). University team and seniors shared experiences and perspectives. Nothing was imposed on the other. Based on this interaction it was possible to establish a perspective on seniors as “human beings that can produce knowledge on many subjects, including Mathematics by means of collaboration” (Lima et al., 2019, p. 1336).

In the following, we bring details of some activities developed during the *Encontro com Matemática*.

Exploring the tangram

This was one of the most appreciated activities by the participants because of the challenge involved in it. At first, it was presented some historical aspect of Tangram. It was told about legends. After that, was disposed a set of pieces for each participant and we started a conversation about the relationship between the Tangram pieces. It was proposed many challenges of image composition using the pieces as illustrated in Image 1 (Lima, 2015, p. 152).

Image 1: Lady manipulating a Tangram

Reading and discussing numeric and graphic information

This activity was also highly successful among the seniors. It involved a conversation about news that are circulated in terms of numeric and graphic information. The activity could

start with a video followed by a discussion on the message one could get from the video. Figure 1⁵ illustrate points that were discussed about the skewed graphics. Another example is a conversation on fake news. This happened in 2018 during the president election period in Brazil. We talked about the veracity of the shared news on social media.

Figure 1: Deceptive Graphics

Mathematics of Bingo

The Bingo is a well-known game by the senior community. It is something so simple that does not require high-cost material. They also like it because there are prizes and a spirit of healthy competitiveness.

Image 2: Overview of Bingo day

⁵ These graphics can be visited on <http://www.semanaon.com.br/coluna/3/553/o-jornalismo-que-se-apresenta-aos-brasileiros> and <https://noticias.uol.com.br/politica/eleicoes/2018/noticias/2018/05/30/psdb-sp-divulga-grafico-desproporcional-de-doria-e-tira-do-ar-apos-criticas.htm>. Last access in 03/24/21.

Opening the university for seniors: A possibility for inclusive mathematics education

In our meetings, Bingo was transformed into an activity that involved mental calculation, mathematical curiosities, and popular knowledge. For example: the number two was called by *the only number that is even and prime*; the number 45 was mentioned as *three quarters of the minutes of an hour*; 54 by *four dozen and a half*, and 51 was called *a good idea*, referring to the name of a popular cachaça. It was necessary to have a calm rhythm that most of the seniors could figure out what number was called. There were prizes for different achievement. The most important was when one completed first all the numbers in a card as shown in image 3. During the whole game was established a very friendly atmosphere. Image 2 presents an overview of what this environment was like.

Image 3: lady playing Bingo

Contribution from the *Encontro com a Matemática*

Through these years, the *Encontro com a Matemática* has become a learning environment for the seniors and for the university team. The research carried out on this environment has identified contribution in aspects such as: social representation about Mathematics, quality of life, intergenerational relationship.

The first aspect is related to Scagion's (2018) research (first author of this paper) that identified the social representations of Mathematics presented by seniors. Scagion was inspired by social representation theory as elaborated by Serge Moscovici who states that social representation is:

a modality of particular knowledge that has the function of elaborating behaviours and communication among individuals, and that in turn also contributes to the processes of formatting behaviour and orientation of social communications (Moscovici, 1978, p. 77).

According to Jodelet (1985), a social representation is “a manner to interpret and think of our daily reality, a way of social knowledge” (p. 360).

Scagion interviewed seniors who attended the *Encontros* to ask about schooling, daily life, work, quality of life, and future. The analysis identified the following representations:

Mathematics is everything; Mathematics helps in the quality of life; it is good for the elderly to understand Mathematics; the relationship with Mathematics change over time and Mathematics is for few people (Scagion, 2018, p. 8).

Alcides (84⁶) Eu gostaria de aprender muita coisa. [...] É o que estou fazendo, aprendendo alguma coisa que nunca aprendi, aqui no curso que nós fizemos, e acho que isso vai além, mas tem aquela história do tempo. (Scagion, 2018, p. 87)

Alcides (84) I would like to learn many things. [...] This is what I am doing here, learning something that I have never learned. Here at the course that we attend, and I think it goes beyond, but there is always that story about time. (Scagion, 2018, p. 87, our translation)

Deisy (80) A minha relação com a Matemática é confortável, porque eu consegui vencê-la, antes era um tabu, que não me deixava satisfeita. Eu tinha que decorá-la e não compreende-la, agora eu a compreendo e a aceito. (Scagion, 2018, p. 79)

Deisy (80) My relationship with Mathematics is comfortable because I was able to beat it. Previously it [Mathematics] was a taboo, that did not make me satisfied. I had to memorize it and did not understand it. Now I can understand and accept it. (Scagion, 2018, p. 79, our translation)

A second aspect in the *Encontros* is related to a quality of life. Life quality is related with material as well as emotional well-being. It depends on the good interpersonal relationships and opportunities of participating in society. This aspect is a result of the research which is presented in detail in Lima (2015) and Lima et al. (2019). The data were produced during the *Encontro com a Matemática*⁷ by means of notes, interviews and video. The analysis

reveals an active engagement of the women and men in the project as well as provides some indication about contributions to the seniors. About their engagement, we considered: a) their interest in discussing the subjects during the meetings; b) their persistence to perform mathematics tasks on their own; c) their argumentation about the ideas showed; and d) their movement of sharing the activities with other people who were not participating in the project. In relation to contribution to senior people, we considered manifestations that expressed: a) improvement of cognitive aspects; b) opportunity for social interaction; and c) the possibility of learning new subjects related to mathematics. (Lima et al., 2019, p. 1332, our translation)

The way the *Encontros* were organized favoured elements connected to quality of life. They could interact with a theme, Mathematics, which was for many of them the reason for evading the school when they were young. In the *Encontros* they had the experience of success. Social integration is essential for the improvement of quality of life. Tasks which stimulated oral presentation, logical reasoning and the dialogical interaction were important approaches. Let the participants tell us what they felt.

Davi (67) [...] abriu a nossa mente [dele e da esposa], abriu o nosso raciocínio. A gente começou a trabalhar com a mente. Entendeu? A, realmente, querer ver e tentar fazer, de ver pronto. Quando eu não consigo resolver alguma coisa, ou, quando você me pergunta alguma coisa assim muito rápida, dá uma bateadeira aqui na cabeça. Sabe? É uma sensação difícil de explicar.

⁶ age

⁷ Lima data production was from 2011 to 2012 and that time the activity was called *Conversas sobre Matemática* (Conversations about Mathematics).

Opening the university for seniors: A possibility for inclusive mathematics education

E eu sinto isso não só nas suas aulas [faz referência às outras atividades do AtivaMente desenvolvidas pelo grupo da Educação Física], que é um sinal que eu estou colocando alguma coisa na cachola, não só nas suas aulas, como em outras aulas, que a gente ocupe a mente, a memória. Para mim, estudar Matemática aqui com você é um pouco desconforto, porque mexe comigo. Entende? Mas o que conta é que é muito benéfica. Porque tem que movimentar a cabeça, porque é uma questão de raciocínio essas atividades. (Lima, 2015, p. 93)

Davi (67) [...] opened our mind [him and his wife], opened our reasoning. We started to work with the mind. Did you understand? To really want to see and to try out, to see it done. When I cannot solve something, or, when you ask me something very fast, it mixes everything in the head. You know? It is a difficult sensation to explain. And I feel it not only in your classes [he refers to other activities of AtivaMente developed by the Physical Education group], which is a signal that I am putting something into the box [head], not only in your classes, as in other classes, that we put our mind into work, the memory. To me, studying Mathematics here with you cause a little discomfort because shake me. You understand me? But what counts is that it is greatly beneficial because we must move on our mind. Because these activities have to do with logic reasoning. (Lima, 2015, p. 93, our translation).

And Ju (60) reinforces this contribution:

A gente, às vezes, fica sem lembrar algumas coisas, sem memorizar. Então, com a ajuda de vocês, a Matemática tem ajudado. Eu memorizo bem números. Pelo fato de estar sempre utilizando telefone, números diversos e o Bingo [Matemático] ajuda muito. Resumindo, todas as atividades da Matemática são boas. Por exemplo, aquelas de blocos de madeira [Blocos Lógicos] foi excelente [...]. Tem algumas coisas que você passa a pensar em relação ao que você ouviu e então a gente acaba também colocando no dia-a-dia da gente. Isso melhora a qualidade da vida da gente. No memorizar, no se concentrar, se organizar. (Lima, 2015, p. 95)

We, sometimes, cannot remember things, without memorizing. So, with your help, Mathematics has helped. I memorize the numbers well. By the fact of always using the telephone, many numbers, and the Bingo [Mathematics] helps a lot. Summarizing, all the Mathematics activities are good. For example, the wooden blocks [Logic Blocks] were excellent [...]. There are some things you start to relate with what we heard and then we end up putting it into our daily lives. It improves our quality of life. In memorizing, concentrating, organizing. (Lima, 2015, p. 95, our translation).

Davi continues,

A gente [a esposa e ele] gostou de tudo. Inclusive, desafiei o meu neto a fazer um Tangram [montar algumas figuras com o Tangram] e ele não conseguiu sozinho. Foi muito bom, porque eu expliquei a ele como se fazia para encaixar as peças. Ele prestou atenção, quando eu falei que tinha que olhar as peças para formar os lados que eram iguais e as figuras que as peças podiam formar. Assim, dava para fazer o todo [montar a figura que se pretendia] (Lima, 2015, p. 154)

We [his wife and him] liked everything. So much so that, I challenged my grandson to make a Tangram [to set up some figures with the Tangram] and he could not do it by himself. It was very good because I explained to him how it should be done to fit the pieces. He paid attention, when I said he had to look to the pieces to make the side that were equal and the figures that

the pieces could form. So, we could make the full piece [to set up the expected figure] (Lima, 2015, p. 154, our translation).

A third aspect to be highlighted is the intergenerational relationship occurred in a *Encontro com a Matemática*. We understand intergenerationality as an interaction between groups of different generations, relating experiences, opinions, cultures and knowledge. According to Hatton-Yeo and Ohsako (2001) intergenerationality is a vehicle to an exchange of knowledge between generations looking for individual and social benefits.

In the UnATI activities, young university students and seniors shared life experiences and established bonds. Intergenerationality provides a resignification of old age, both by seniors and young people. According to Mendes, Leandro and Lopes (2017), spaces of intergenerational interaction can be beneficial for the establishment of bonds and social practices that provide inclusion.

Final considerations

Encontro com a Matemática departure from the perspective of promoting the appreciation of senior's life, which means right to education, health and enjoyment. During the meetings, it was imperative that the environment was encouraging for everyone to feel free to share their ideas, doubts and life experience. This was achieved through dialogic communication.

By this article we hope to show the importance of working with Mathematics Education for seniors in an inclusive perspective. The *Encontro com a Matemática* starts from the perspective of promoting the value of life for the elderly, which means the right to education, health and entertainment. It is organized as a space for activities that rely on dialogue between young and seniors. During the meetings, it was essential that the environment was stimulating so that everyone felt free to share their ideas, doubts and life experiences. This was achieved through dialogic communication. Communication during the performance of activities provided reflections on meeting differences, the need to promote quality of life for the elderly, concern with accessibility.

Intergenerationality contributes to all the publics involved and the social relationships of these people. For the elderly, it contributes to promoting quality of life. On the other hand, it contributes to the reinterpretation of young people based on reflections on the interaction with the elderly. Young people can think about their future as an elderly person. For society in general, the contribution can come as valuing the elderly and reducing prejudice and violence.

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Opening the university for seniors: A possibility for inclusive mathematics education

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